

Cholesterolic Granuloma of the Ovary: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Cholesterol granuloma is the consequence of a chronic inflammatory reaction due to the accumulation of cholesterol crystals in the tissues. The symptoms, clinical examination and preoperative imaging of cholesterol granuloma may be misdiagnosed as ovarian cancer. Since the final diagnosis of a pelvic mass depends on histopathological findings, cholesterol granuloma should be borne in mind as a differential diagnosis of pelvic mass.

Keywords: Cholesterol granuloma; Ovary; Surgery

INTRODUCTION

Cholesterol granuloma is the result of a chronic inflammatory reaction caused by the accumulation of cholesterol crystals in tissues. Although it occurs in many parts of the body, its most common site is the ear ^[1]. It is a rare benign tumor-like lesion, rarely affecting the female genital tract ^[2]. Diagnosis is difficult despite radiological and biological examinations, which require histological confirmation to rule out a malignant tumor of the ovary. In our case, a patient was referred to the gynecology department with a suspicious ovarian mass, but was diagnosed with a cholesterol granuloma of the ovary.

CASE PRESENTATION

Our patient was 38 years old, with no particular pathological history, who consulted us for abdominal distension with no associated urinary or digestive signs, all evolving in a context of conservation of general condition. Clinical examination revealed abdominal distension with a positive icicle sign (Figure 1), and speculum examination revealed a cervix deviated to the left, with vaginal touch and abdominal palpation revealing the

lower pole of a right latero-uterine mass. Pelvic ultrasound revealed a uterus of normal size and echostructure, measuring 73x48x40mm, with a cystic formation of finely echogenic fluid measuring 20x14cm, right and left ovaries not seen and no pelvic adenopathy (Figure 2).

Abdominal-pelvic CT showed an abdominal-pelvic cystic mass measuring 35x26x14cm with partitions without a fleshy component, normal-sized uterus and absence of deep adenopathy (Figure 3). Biological tests showed CA125 to be 1720U/ml, and all other tumour markers were negative.

An exploratory laparotomy was performed intraoperatively, and the omentum was firmly adherent to the anterior abdominal wall and pelvic region. After adhesiolysis, an immobile mass of irregular contours measuring approximately 30cm was found, taking up the entire abdomino-pelvic cavity. During dissection, a yellow-brown fluid was drained from the ruptured area of the mass. The uterus was of normal size and contour, while the left ovary was adherent to the sigmoid colon. The right ovary was also adherent to the right side of the pelvic wall. A right cystectomy was performed with abundant saline lavage.

Microscopic examination showed longitudinal cleft aggregates of cholesterol crystals surrounded by lymphocytes, foamy histiocytes, neutrophils and numerous multinucleated giant cells including a cholesterol granuloma in adipose tissue. Lymphocytes and hemolyzed erythrocytes were noted in the peritoneal fluid. A definitive diagnosis of cholesterol granuloma was made, with no evidence of malignancy (Figure 4). The patient was discharged on postoperative day 3.

Figure 1 : Abdominal distension.

Figure 2: Aspect d'une formation kystique cloisonnée.

Figure 3: Masse kystique cloisonnée sans composante charnue.

Figure 4 : Histological appearance of a cholesterol granuloma

DISCUSSION

Cholesterol granuloma was first described in 1917 by Manase. According to the literature, it mainly affects middle-aged men rather than women ^[3]. Most cases are associated with the head and neck region, with a few cases reported involving organs such as the breast, kidney, anterior mediastinum and ovary ^[4,5]. Ovarian cholesterol granuloma is a rare entity that may mimic ovarian cancer clinically and radiologically but confirm on histopathological findings.

Although histological examination shows a foreign-body reaction to cholesterol crystals, there is no clear consensus on the precise etiopathogenesis. Moreover, the molecular mechanism of cholesterol granuloma formation in the cyst wall has yet to be identified ^[6]. It has non-specific features of chronic inflammation. Since inflammation occurs against cholesterol crystals, a foreign-body reaction is revealed by the accumulation of histiocytes, multinucleated giant cells, foamy macrophages, neutrophils, hemosiderin-laden macrophages and cholesterol clefts ^[7]. Blood and inflammatory tissue degradation products affect foreign body giant cells, leading to fibrosis. Cholesterol crystals may originate from disintegrated erythrocyte cell membranes, plasma lipids or fatty degeneration of connective tissue in a cyst blocked by inflammation. In our case, histopathological examination showed similar features.

The formation of cholesterol granulomas leads to inflammation, fibrosis and adhesions between the granuloma and adjacent organs, which are observed during surgery.

The presence of cholesterol granulomas has rarely been reported in the female genitalia. Sumathi represented a 65-year-old woman with an endometrial cholesterol granuloma suffering from urine leakage and constipation ^[8]. In breast imaging studies, it has been established that cholesterol granuloma can mimic breast cancer ^[9]. Our case is the second reported in the literature with suspected ovarian cancer ^[10].

Ovarian cancer presents several diagnostic challenges. Currently, no serum biomarker is both highly sensitive and specific for the diagnosis of cancer. Thus, we have combined test results, serum markers and radiological images to improve detection of malignancies. CA 125 is the most widely used serum biomarker for the assessment of an adnexal mass, although it is increased in many benign conditions. . In our case, it might have

been more accurate to perform an MRI during the preoperative study of the patient. Since cholesterol granuloma contains mainly lipids, surgery is essential to make

CONCLUSION

The symptoms, clinical examination and preoperative imaging of cholesterol granuloma may be misdiagnosed as ovarian cancer. Since the final diagnosis of a pelvic mass depends on histopathological findings, cholesterol granuloma should be kept in mind as a differential diagnosis of pelvic mass.

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